

Supplementary Materials for
Cloaking a tunable magneto-elastic metastructure for energy
harvesting and vibration suppression

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This PDF file includes:

Materials and Methods

Supplementary Text

Figures S1 to S26

Tables S1 to S3

Captions for Movies S1 to S6

Other Supplementary Materials for this manuscript:

Movies S1 to S6

Materials and Methods

Fabrication and assembly

The host beam, resonators, and reinforcement frames are all fabricated using carbon fiber. The precise dimensions of these components are obtained using a CNC milling machine. The reinforcement and added mass are fixed on the beam using a structural adhesive with shear stress resistance (3M Scotch-Weld DP460). Piezoelectric (PZT-Lead zirconate titanate, PZT-5J, S118-J1SS-1808YB Mide Technology) patches are bonded to the surface of the resonators with the same adhesive. The electrodes of the patches are connected in parallel to a resistor on an electronic protoboard, with each resonator having its resistive circuit. A permanent cylindrical Neodymium magnet is fixed on the tip of the resonator beam using a 3D-printed magnet holder. In front of this magnet, another identical magnet oriented to face the same polarity (to create repulsive magnetic force) is fixed using an adjustable holder that allows manual control of the distance between the magnets. Additional details regarding the fabrication and assembly of the metastructure can be found in Movie S6 and the Supplementary Text - Section Fabrication and assembly of the physical prototype.

Experimental setup

The experimental setup used to perform the vibration tests is shown in Fig. S1A. The metabeam is clamped to an electromagnetic shaker (TIRA vib 51144) which is placed on an optical table (Nexus Optical Table, from Thorlabs) to prevent spurious vibrations and to isolate the metabeam from the surrounding environment. Details of the cloaked metabeam equipped with magneto-elastic piezoelectric resonators are illustrated in the zoomed-in view of Fig. S1A. The restoring force of the resonator can be manually controlled by using the adjustable magnet holder. Figure S1B shows the resonator with a short distance between the magnets, which exhibits bistable behavior (the photo shows the beam on its stable equilibrium point on the right side; the other stable equilibrium point is located on the left). Figure. S1C shows the resonator with a long distance between the magnets, which exhibits a monostable behavior. Vibration experiments are conducted by imposing an up-sweep frequency excitation. A vibration controller (VR9500 4 channels, 26000 lines of resolution) driven by Vibration View software is used to ensure the desired amplitude and frequency values at

the base of the metastructure. An accelerometer (PCB 356A45) is mounted on this base to provide the feedback signal. Additional tests are also conducted using a fixed single frequency. More details about the experiment procedures are presented in the SI Appendix - Section Vibration experiments.

Numerical simulations

The dimensions of the reinforcement and the added mass are determined by an optimization algorithm in Matlab, using Eqs. 1, 2, and 3 as objective functions. A 3D ABAQUS finite element simulation for cloaking validation is developed and described in the Supplementary Text - Section Cloaking design. This validation is compared with experimental tests, with detailed procedures in the Supplementary Text - Section Cloaking design. The modeling of the metastructure with the magneto-elastic piezoelectric resonators is described in the Supplementary Text - Section Metabeam with magneto-elastic piezoelectric resonators. The numerical methods for solving the equations of motion using MATLAB are presented in this section of the Supplementary Text.

Figure S1: Experimental setup of the cloaked metastructure equipped with magneto-elastic piezoelectric resonators. (A) Photo of the metastructure clamped on an electromagnetic shaker which is mounted on an optical table. A zoomed-in view of the red-marked region highlights the detailed arrangement of the resonators and the cloaking design. Each resonator is equipped with piezoelectric patches bonded to both surfaces and a cylindrical permanent magnet on its tip. At the bottom, a 3D-printed connector is used to establish the electrical connections to the piezoelectric layers. At the top, an adjustable magnet holder carries an identical magnet, enabling repulsive force interactions between the magnets. This holder provides a manual adjustment of the distance d . Additional structural details of the reinforcement design and the added masses are also shown. (B) Photo of the resonator with the magnets positioned close together, creating a bistable state. This setup results in two stable equilibrium points, with one shown in the image (shifted to the right) and the other shifted to the left. (C) Photo of the resonator with the magnets positioned farther apart, creating a monostable state. In this case, there is only one stable equilibrium point aligned along the neutral axis of the beam.

Supplementary Text

Cloaking design

We adopt a cloaking strategy based on the reinforcement of the boundaries and mass redistribution to render the voids embedded in the beam invisible to elastic wave propagation; in other words, dynamically equivalent to an intact beam. To achieve this equivalence, we reinforce the boundaries of the voids with a frame whose dimensions were determined to exactly compensate for the flexural and torsional rigidities removed by creating the voids. In addition to the rigidities, the removed mass and mass moment of inertia were also conserved (*I*).

Building on (*I*), which proposed a method to hide square voids, we generalize this cloaking design to hide rectangular voids. In the following, we provide a detailed mathematical formulation for the cloaking design and Finite Element Simulations to demonstrate its effectiveness. Furthermore, we validate our approach through experimental modal analysis by comparing an uncloaked beam with a cloaked beam.

Mathematical formulation

The removed part of the beam (void) is considered as an isotropic elastic plate described by the equation of motion (considering the z -displacement) as (see (45) for more details)

$$D \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2D \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + D \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} = q, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where q is a distributed load and D is the bending rigidity of the plate (E Young's Modulus, t thickness and ν Poisson's ratio)

$$D = \frac{Et^3}{12(1 - \nu^2)}. \quad (\text{S2})$$

The elastic reinforcement frame consists of a system of beams, with two beams spaced along the x -direction and two beams spaced along the y -direction, rigidly connected at their points of intersection. According to (45), this reinforcement is modeled by an anisotropic elastic plate described as

$$D_x \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^4} + 2H \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + D_y \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} = q. \quad (\text{S3})$$

Considering a symmetrical reinforcement along x and y axes, the bending and torsional rigidities are described as

$$D_x = \frac{B_x}{d_x}, \quad D_y = \frac{B_y}{d_y}, \quad 2H = \frac{C_x}{d_x} + \frac{C_y}{d_y} \quad (\text{S4})$$

where $B_x = EJ_x$ and $B_y = EJ_y$ are the flexural rigidities of the beam parallel to the x and y axes, respectively; d_x and d_y are the distances from the beams to the x and y axes, respectively; $C_x = GJ_{t,x}$ and $C_y = GJ_{t,y}$ are the torsional rigidities of the beams parallel to the x and y axes, respectively.

The anisotropic elastic plates must have the same flexural and torsional rigidities of the isotropic plate. Therefore, we impose

$$\frac{B_x}{d_x} = \frac{B_y}{d_y} = \frac{Et^3}{12(1-\nu^2)} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{C_x}{d_x} + \frac{C_y}{d_y} = \frac{Et^3}{6(1-\nu^2)}. \quad (\text{S5})$$

Furthermore, the removed mass (M_p) and moment of inertia (I_p) must be compensated. To achieve this, additional masses (m_i) are added to the reinforcement mass (M) to fully compensate the mass (M_p) and the moment of inertia (I_p) removed during the creation of the voids. These considerations imply that the placement of these masses must ensure both mass and inertia equivalence, satisfying the following conditions

$$M_p = M + \sum_i^N m_i \quad \text{and} \quad I_p = I + \sum_i^N m_i \tilde{d}_i^2. \quad (\text{S6})$$

where I is the moment of inertia of mass of the reinforcement grid, and \tilde{d}_i is the distance of each mass from the mid axes.

Validation analysis: simulation and experiment

In our system, a reinforcement grid is designed to cloak a void that measures $118 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$. Figure S2 illustrates the reinforcement in detail. A crossbar with a width, b_c , of 7 mm is added to the grid in the y axis to clamp the piezoelectric resonator, as we discuss above. This value is defined considering the recommendation of the piezoelectric manufacturer. Therefore, the crossbar separates the void into two parts: a larger hole ($103 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$) that houses the piezoelectric beam and a smaller hole ($8 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$) for accessing the electrical connections of the piezoelectric patches. Furthermore, this reinforcement is bonded on both sides of the beam to preserve the symmetry of the beam with respect to its medial axis.

To calculate the dimensions of the reinforcement, we define $d_x = a_x/2 + b_x$ and $d_y = a_y/2 + b_y$, where a_x and a_y are the dimensions of the void in x and y direction, respectively. The moments of

inertia of the beams at x direction is $J_x = 1/12b_y(t + 2h_t)^3$ and at y direction is $J_y = 1/24(b_x + \bar{b}_x + b_c)(t + 2h_t)^3$, where b_y is the width of the beam of the reinforcement at x direction; and b_x and \bar{b}_x are the width of the beams at y direction, as shown in S2. b_c is the width of the crossbar that is equal to 7 mm, as mentioned previously, and h_t is the thickness of the reinforcement.

The dimensions b_x , \bar{b}_x , b_y and h_t are calculated based on Eqs. S5. The values of the added masses m_i are also calculated based on Eqs. S6. A Matlab code is developed to obtain these values.

Based on this numerical procedure, the optimal reinforcement dimensions are $b_x = 7.15$ mm, $\bar{b}_x = 0.55$ mm, $b_y = 2.08$ mm, and $h_t = 1.08$ mm, with added masses of 5.3 g (mass m_3 aligned on the x direction) and 0.38 g (masses m_1 and m_2 aligned on the y direction). To facilitate the manufacture process, we adopt $b_x = 7.1$ mm, $\bar{b}_x = 1$ mm, $b_y = 2.1$ mm, and $h_t = 1.1$ mm. Further results demonstrate that this approximation does not compromise the cloaking performance.

Figure S2: Details of the cloaking design using reinforcement grid and added masses to hide a rectangular void.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the cloaking design, we conduct finite element numerical simulation using ABAQUS. Initially, we implement the cloaking design on a cantilever beam with dimensions of $985 \times 45 \times 2$ mm³ with seven rectangular voids measuring 118×30 mm², as the metastructure proposed in this paper (see Figure S3A). The beam is subjected to sinusoidal base excitation with null rotation, inducing elastic wave propagations in the beam. About 25000 quadratic tetrahedral elements of type C3D10 are employed to discretize the structure. The eigenmodes and the steady-state frequency response are obtained using the Lanczos solver. To check the accuracy of cloaking, we use the natural frequencies of the transverse mode for the intact beam, uncloaked

Table S1: Natural frequencies of the initial six transverse modes for the cantilever beam under intact, cloaked, and uncloaked conditions. The scattering reduction coefficients (SRC) for each mode are also displayed.

	1 st mode	2 nd mode	3 th mode	4 th mode	5 th mode	6 th mode
Intact beam	2.27 Hz	14.27 Hz	39.98 Hz	78.38 Hz	129.65 Hz	193.84 Hz
Uncloaked beam	2.01 Hz	12.61 Hz	35.42 Hz	69.61 Hz	115.39 Hz	172.46 Hz
Cloaked beam	2.27 Hz	14.28 Hz	40.03 Hz	78.46 Hz	129.32 Hz	190.49 Hz
SRC	0.0000	0.0060	0.0110	0.0091	0.0231	0.1567

beam (voids without reinforcements), and cloaked beam (voids with reinforcements). Results of finite element model simulations are reported in Figure S3. The scattering reduction coefficient (SRC) is then computed as a measure of cloaking accuracy,

$$\text{SRC} = \frac{f^c - f^i}{f^v - f^i} \quad (\text{S7})$$

depending on the eigenvalues of the cloaked structure, f^c , the uncloaked structure, f^v , and the intact structure, f^i . When the SRC is equal to 0, signify that the cloaking design is perfect, i.e., the cloaked structure behaves identically to an intact one. Conversely, an SRC equal to 1 implies that the cloaking is inefficient, and a value superior to 1 means that the uncloaked structure behaves more similarly to an intact structure than the cloaked one. Figure S3B demonstrates the SRC for the initial six transverse modes, with their respective values reported in Table S1. The results demonstrate that the cloaking design has an excellent performance, with the transversal natural frequencies of the cloaked beam differing by less than 1% compared to the intact beam. The transverse mode shapes associated with the first three frequencies are reported in Figure S3C. The efficacy of the cloaking mechanism becomes evident upon comparing the behaviors of beams with cloaked and uncloaked voids. The cloaked beam dynamically behaves almost identically to the intact beam, whereas the uncloaked beam displays significant differences, since when the intact and cloaked beams are in the resonance, the uncloaked beam is far from the resonance condition.

The beam with voids and the reinforcements are fabricated as described in the Section Fabrication and assembly of the physical prototype. Free vibration tests are conducted to determine the first natural frequencies of the uncloaked and cloaked beams. For each test, the beam is fixed on the

Figure S3: Finite-element simulation results of the cloaking performance on a cantilever beam with seven rectangular voids. (A) Setup of intact, uncloaked, and cloaked beams. One end of the beams is clamped, while the other end is free to vibrate. A sinusoidal base vibration with null rotation is applied along the y-axis. (B) Illustration of the Scattering Reduction Coefficient (SRC) for the initial six resonance modes of the cantilever beam. (C) Eigenmodes of the intact beam (on the left), the uncloaked beam (in the middle), and the cloaked beam (on the right) for the first (i), second (ii), third (iii), and fourth modes (iv).

Figure S4: Experimental validation of the cloaking design. (A) Fast Fourier Transform of the velocity measured on the tip of the beam for the cloaked and uncloaked beam under free vibration. (B) Comparison between the natural frequencies in Hz obtained from the experiment and the numerical results. (C) Percent error between the numerical and experimental natural frequencies of the cloaked and uncloaked beams.

shaker, and a single impact is applied at the midpoint of the beam. The velocity field is measured using the VIC-3D system (described in Section Experimental setup), and the response of the system in the frequency domain is obtained through Fast Fourier Transform analysis.

The experimental results, including their natural frequencies, are shown in Fig. S4. Figure S4A shows that the frequency responses of the uncloaked and cloaked beams are notably distinct. The resonance conditions of these structures are defined in different frequency ranges, mainly for higher natural frequency values. Figure S4B shows a comparison between the experimental and numerical results of the uncloaked and cloaked beams. The experimental frequencies align closely with those obtained from finite element simulations, as confirmed by the percentage error shown in Fig. S4C. These findings demonstrate the reliability of the experimental and numerical methods.

To explore the efficacy of cloaking in scenarios where flexural and torsional modes are strongly coupled, we use a plate model. The same finite element simulations are conducted, but considering a plate of dimensions $750 \times 500 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ with nine rectangular voids of dimensions $118 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$, as shown in Figure S5. One end of the plate is clamped, while the opposite end is free to vibrate. The structure is excited by sinusoidal base excitation with null rotation. The SRCs are calculated for frequencies ranging from 0 to 260 Hz, exploring a broader band compared to the beam case. The

Table S2: Natural frequencies for the cantilever plate under intact, cloaked, and uncloaked conditions. The scattering reduction coefficients (SRC) for each mode are also displayed.

mode	Intact plate	Uncloaked plate	Cloaked plate	SRC
1	4.04 Hz	3.94 Hz	4.02 Hz	0.2629
2	13.64 Hz	13.12 Hz	13.37 Hz	0.5278
3	25.12 Hz	24.66 Hz	25.16 Hz	0.0943
4	46.10 Hz	44.40 Hz	45.27 Hz	0.4918
5	62.60 Hz	53.49 Hz	59.33 Hz	0.3596
6	72.16 Hz	69.63 Hz	71.65 Hz	0.2014
7	94.29 Hz	91.11 Hz	92.97 Hz	0.4139
8	100.27 Hz	91.32 Hz	95.71 Hz	0.5097
9	142.36 Hz	136.37 Hz	140.26 Hz	0.3506
10	158.06 Hz	146.80 Hz	151.63 Hz	0.5710
11	201.00 Hz	175.05 Hz	187.24 Hz	0.5303
12	232.09 Hz	227.00 Hz	233.50 Hz	0.2770
13	256.14 Hz	249.05 Hz	252.64 Hz	0.4937

results are shown in Figure S5 and reported in Table S2. It is shown that the SRC ranges within the interval (0.0943, 0.5710), demonstrating excellent cloaking performance, with natural frequencies of the cloaked plate differing by less than 4.1% compared to the intact plate. The eigenmodes at different specific frequencies involving flexural and torsional vibrations are reported in Figure S5C for intact plate, cloaked plate, and uncloaked plate. The cloaked plate behaves almost identically to the intact plate at these frequency conditions, while the uncloaked plate displayed significant differences.

Figure S5: Finite-element simulation results of the cloaking performance of a plate with nine rectangular voids showing coupled flexural and torsional modes. (A) Setup of intact, uncloaked, and cloaked plates. One end of the plates is clamped, while the other end is free to vibrate. A sinusoidal base excitation with null rotation is applied along the z -axis. (B) Illustration of the Scattering Reduction Coefficient (SRC) for frequencies ranging from 0 to 250Hz. (C) Eigenmodes of the intact plate (on the left), the uncloaked plate (in the middle), and the cloaked plate (on the right) for different frequencies (i) 25.20 Hz, (ii) 72.00 Hz, and (iii) 140.80 Hz.

Metabeam with magneto-elastic piezoelectric resonators

The proposed metastructure is designed based on the local resonance phenomenon, where the phase velocity of the resonator is lower than that of the host beam. When the frequency of an elastic incident wave matches the natural frequency of the resonator, part of the wave is reflected by the resonator. This creates a local resonance bandgap, which attenuates the energy transmitted along the structure. Our work aims to harvest this energy concentrated in the resonator and convert it into electricity.

We design the resonator as a magneto-elastic piezoelectric cantilever beam. The piezoelectric material is introduced to convert the kinetic energy into electrical energy. The magneto-elastic interaction is defined as a permanent magnet inserted on the tip of the beam and another permanent magnet in front of its face. It introduces an intentional nonlinearity and allows us to control the restoring force of the resonator. In the following, we describe the nonlinear magnet interacting force between the magnets, the mathematical background of the equation of motion of the metabeam, and numerical results to demonstrate the capability of vibration suppression and energy harvesting of the metastructure.

Nonlinear magnetic force

Nonlinearity is intentionally introduced into the resonators by placing two permanent magnets, one at the tip of the beam (magnet A) and another fixed at the rigid base near the free end of the beam (magnet B), as shown in Figure S6. They are positioned to face each other with the same magnet pole, causing a repulsive magnetic force.

The magnetic force intensity primarily depends on the physical properties of the magnets and the distance between the centers of magnets, denoted as $|\mathbf{r}|$, where \mathbf{r} is the vector from the position of one dipole to the position of the other. As this distance decreases, the magnetic force increases. Numerous references described the interaction of this magnetic force, for example in (50–52). For this analysis, we calculate the magnetic flux density (\mathbf{B}_{BA}) generated by magnet B upon magnet A given by

$$\mathbf{B}_{BA} = -\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \nabla \frac{\boldsymbol{\mu}_B \cdot \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}|^3}, \quad (\text{S8})$$

where μ_0 is the permeability of space, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_B$ is the magnetic moment of dipole B. The potential energy

Figure S6: Nonlinear magneto-elastic piezoelectric resonator beam. The system consists of a cantilever beam of length l_{beam} with piezoelectric patches fixed to the region of maximum deformation on both surfaces. Permanent magnets are fixed at the tip of the beam and at the rigid base. They are concentric and positioned to face each other with the same pole. (A) Illustration of the nonlinear magneto-elastic piezoelectric beam. The superimposed light gray beam represents the beam in an undeformed condition. (B) Schematic analysis of the system. The fixed end of the beam is represented as point O . Point A indicates the center of magnet A in a deformed condition and the point A_0 its position in an undeformed condition. The point A mapped in the horizontal direction is denoted by point C . Point B is the center of magnet B.

is

$$U_m = -\mathbf{B}_{BA} \cdot \boldsymbol{\mu}_A = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \nabla \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\mu}_B \cdot \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}|^3} \right) \cdot \boldsymbol{\mu}_A, \quad (\text{S9})$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_A$ is the magnetic moment of dipole A. The magnetic force on dipole A exerted by dipole B is derived from potential energy by

$$\mathbf{F}_B = -\nabla U_m = -\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \nabla \left[\left(\nabla \frac{\boldsymbol{\mu}_B \cdot \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}|^3} \right) \cdot \boldsymbol{\mu}_A \right]. \quad (\text{S10})$$

By mathematical operations, the final magnetic force is

$$\mathbf{F}_B = \frac{3\mu_0\mu_A\mu_B}{4\pi r^4} [\hat{\mathbf{r}} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_A \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_B) + \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_B (\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_A \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}) + \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_A (\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_B \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}) - 5\hat{\mathbf{r}} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_A \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}) (\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_B \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}})], \quad (\text{S11})$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_A$, and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_B$ are the unit vectors in the direction of \mathbf{r} , $\boldsymbol{\mu}_A$, and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_B$, respectively.

The dot product of Eq. S11 can be expressed using the angles from the geometry of the system reported in Fig. S6. By substituting the trigonometric relationship of the angles as defined in Fig.S6, we simplify the magnetic force as

$$\mathbf{F}_B = \frac{3\mu_0\mu_A\mu_B}{4\pi r^4} (\hat{\mathbf{r}} \cos \theta + \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_B \cos \alpha + \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_A \cos \beta - 5\hat{\mathbf{r}} \cos \alpha \cos \beta). \quad (\text{S12})$$

We assume that the transverse displacement of the tip of the beam $u(t)$ has a small value compared to the original distance d between the two magnetic dipoles. Additionally, we assume the magnetic force along $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_x$ negligible because the deflection of the beam is more influenced by the magnetic force in $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_y$ direction. Then the magnetic force in $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_y$ direction is

$$F_{B\hat{\mathbf{e}}_y} = \frac{3\mu_0\mu_A\mu_B}{4\pi r^4} [(\cos \theta - 5 \cos \alpha \cos \beta) \sin \beta + \cos \beta \sin \varphi]. \quad (\text{S13})$$

Based on the geometry shown in Fig. S6, the angles can be obtained following

$$l = OA = l_{beam} + \frac{l_{mag}}{2} \quad (\text{S14})$$

$$e = BC = d + l_{mag} + l(1 - \cos \varphi) \quad (\text{S15})$$

$$r = AB = \sqrt{u(t)^2 + d^2} \quad (\text{S16})$$

$$\sin \theta = \sin \varphi = \frac{AC}{OA} = \frac{u(t)}{l} \quad (\text{S17})$$

$$\cos \theta = -\cos \varphi = -\frac{1}{l} \sqrt{l^2 - u(t)^2} \quad (\text{S18})$$

Figure S7: Schematic illustration of the metastructure based on a cantilever beam with magneto-elastic piezoelectric resonators.

$$\cos \beta = \frac{AC}{AB} = \frac{e}{r} \quad (\text{S19})$$

$$\sin \beta = \frac{BC}{AB} = \frac{u(t)}{r} \quad (\text{S20})$$

$$\cos \alpha = \cos (\theta - \beta) = \cos \theta \cos \beta + \sin \theta \sin \beta = \frac{1}{lr} \left(u(t)^2 - e\sqrt{l^2 - u(t)^2} \right) \quad (\text{S21})$$

Finally, by using trigonometric relations, the magnetic force in direction \hat{e}_y is given by

$$F_{B\hat{e}_y} = \frac{3\mu_0\mu_A\mu_B u(t)}{4\pi r^5 l} \left[e - \sqrt{l^2 - u(t)^2} - \frac{5e}{r^2} \left(u(t)^2 - e\sqrt{l^2 - u(t)^2} \right) \right] \quad (\text{S22})$$

Modeling the governing equations of the metabeam

By cloaking the voids, the behavior of the holed metabeam can be approximated to that of a continuous cantilever beam, with embedded magneto-elastic piezoelectric resonators acting as discrete masses distributed along its length. A schematic illustration of the metabeam is illustrated in Fig. S7.

The cantilever beam is subjected to a base motion excitation. The total transverse displacement, $w_t(x, t)$, of the beam under base excitation is defined as

$$w_t(x, t) = w_b(t) + w(x, t), \quad (\text{S23})$$

where $w_b(t)$ is the base displacement, and $w(x, t)$ is the relative displacement of the beam with respect to its length x and time t .

The metabeam is modeled assuming a Euler-Bernoulli theory with modal damping term, as demonstrated in (53). Discrete masses, representing the resonator masses, are coupled along its length. The governing equations of this system are

$$m_b \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2}(x, t) + c \frac{\partial w}{\partial t}(x, t) + EI \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4}(x, t) - \sum_{j=1}^S \left(c_j \dot{u}_j(t) + k_j u_j(t) - F_{B_{e_y}}(u_j(t)) - \vartheta_j v_j(t) \right) \delta(x - x_j) = -m_b \ddot{w}_b(t) \quad (\text{S24})$$

$$m_j \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2}(x_j, t) + \ddot{u}_j(t) \right) + c_j \dot{u}_j(t) + k_j u_j(t) - F_{B_{e_y}}(u_j(t)) - \vartheta_j v_j(t) = -m_j \ddot{w}_b(t), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, S \quad (\text{S25})$$

$$C_{p,j} \dot{v}_j(t) + \mathcal{Y}_j v_j(t) + \vartheta_j \dot{u}_j(t) = 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, S \quad (\text{S26})$$

where $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac Delta function; u_j and v_j are the displacement and voltage of the j -th resonator, respectively; x_j is the position of the j -th resonator; m_b , c and EI are the mass per length of the beam, the modal damping and the flexural rigidity of the beam, respectively; m_j , c_j and k_j is the mass, the damping and the stiffness of the j -th resonator, respectively; $F_{B_{e_y}}$ is the nonlinear magnetic force; v_j , $C_{p,j}$ and \mathcal{Y}_j are the electromechanical coupling, equivalent piezoelectric capacitance and the electrical admittance of the j -th resonator, respectively; S is the number of resonators. These equations needs to satisfy the boundary conditions for the clamped beam,

$$w(0, t) = 0, \quad \frac{\partial w(0, t)}{\partial x} = 0, \quad EI \frac{\partial^2 w(L, t)}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad EI \frac{\partial^3 w(L, t)}{\partial x^3} = 0 \quad (\text{S27})$$

The Galerkin Method is used to expand the solution using the modal shapes of the cantilever beam without resonators, denoted as $\phi(x)$. The relative displacement of the beam is approximated as

$$w(x, t) \approx \sum_{r=1}^N \eta_r(t) \phi_r(x), \quad (\text{S28})$$

where N represents the number of modes in the expansion, and $\eta_r(t)$ denotes the modal displacement of the r -th mode of the cantilever beam. We neglect the nonlinear modal interactions because the modes of the beam are well-separated. The normalized mass modal shapes of the beam are given by the following equation

$$\phi_r(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{m_b L}} \left[\cos\left(\frac{\lambda_r x}{L}\right) - \cosh\left(\frac{\lambda_r x}{L}\right) + \frac{\sin \lambda_r - \sinh \lambda_r}{\cos \lambda_r + \cosh \lambda_r} \left(\sin\left(\frac{\lambda_r x}{L}\right) - \sinh\left(\frac{\lambda_r x}{L}\right) \right) \right], \quad (\text{S29})$$

where λ_r is the r -th positive real solution of the characteristic equation for cantilever beam given by

$$\cos \lambda \cosh \lambda + 1 = 0. \quad (\text{S30})$$

By satisfying the orthogonality conditions of the modal shapes

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{x=0}^{x=L} \phi_r(x) m_b \phi_s(x) dx &= \delta_{r,s}, \quad r, s = 1, 2, \dots \\ \int_{x=0}^{x=L} \phi_r(x) EI \phi_s''''(x) dx &= \omega_r^2 \delta_{r,s}, \quad r, s = 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S31})$$

and substituting Equation S28 into Equation S24 and Equation S25, we obtain new equations

$$\ddot{\eta}_r + 2\zeta_r \omega_r \dot{\eta}_r + \omega_r^2 \eta_r - \sum_{j=1}^S \left(k_j u_j + c_j \dot{u}_j - F_{B_{e_y}}(u_j) - \vartheta_j v_j \right) \phi_r(x_j) = -m_b \ddot{w}_b \int_{x=0}^{x=L} \phi_r(x) dx \quad (\text{S32})$$

$$m_j \left[\sum_{r=1}^N \ddot{\eta}_r \phi_r + \ddot{u}_j \right] + c_j \dot{u}_j + k_j u_j - F_{B_{e_y}}(u_j) - \vartheta_j v_j = -m_j \ddot{w}_b(t), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, S. \quad (\text{S33})$$

where the natural frequencies ω_r is defined by

$$\omega_r = \lambda_r^2 \sqrt{\left(\frac{EI}{\rho AL^4} \right)}. \quad (\text{S34})$$

Equations S32, S33, and S26 constitute a system of $N+2S$ coupled second-order ordinary differential equations.

This system can be expressed in matrix form as

$$[\mathbf{M}] \ddot{\mathbf{Z}}(t) + [\mathbf{C}] \dot{\mathbf{Z}}(t) + [\mathbf{K}] \mathbf{Z}(t) = \mathbf{F}(t) + \mathbf{F}_B(\mathbf{Z}(t)), \quad (\text{S35})$$

where $\mathbf{Z} = [\eta_1(t), \eta_2(t), \dots, \eta_N(t), u_1(t), u_2(t), \dots, u_S(t), v_1(t), v_2(t), \dots, v_S(t)]^T$ contains the modal weightings of the host beam (η), the relative displacements of the tip of the resonator beam (u), and the dissipated voltage in the circuit (v). The notation ($\dot{\cdot}$) denotes the first derivative with

respect to time, and ($\ddot{}$) represents the second derivative with respect to time. The matrices are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\mathbf{M}] &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{11} & \mathbf{M}_{12} & 0 \\ \mathbf{M}_{21} & \mathbf{M}_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad [\mathbf{C}] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D}_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{D}_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{\Theta} & \mathbf{C}_p \end{bmatrix}, \\
 [\mathbf{K}] &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{K}_{22} & -\mathbf{\Theta} \\ 0 & 0 & \mathbf{Y} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{F}_B(\mathbf{Z}(t)) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \mathbf{F}_B(u_j(t)) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_1 \\ \mathbf{F}_2 \\ \mathbf{F}_3 \end{bmatrix} A_0 \cos(\Omega_0 t),
 \end{aligned} \tag{S36}$$

where \mathbf{M}_{11} is a $N \times N$ matrix, with the entries: $m_{mn} = \delta_{mn} + \sum_{j=1}^S m_j \phi_m(x_j) \phi_n(x_j)$; \mathbf{M}_{12} is a $N \times S$ matrix, with the entries: $m_{mq} = m_q \phi_m(x_q)$; \mathbf{M}_{21} is a $S \times N$ matrix, with the entries: $m_{pn} = m_p \phi_n(x_p)$; \mathbf{M}_{22} is a $S \times S$ matrix, with the entries: $m_{pq} = \delta_{pq} m_p$; \mathbf{C}_p is a $S \times S$ matrix, with the entries: $C_{pq} = \delta_{pq} C_p$; \mathbf{K}_{11} is a $N \times N$ diagonal matrix, with the entries: $k_{mn} = \delta_{mn} \omega_m^2$; \mathbf{K}_{22} is a $S \times S$ diagonal matrix, with the entries: $k_{pq} = \delta_{pq} k_p$; \mathbf{D}_1 is a $N \times N$ diagonal matrix, with the entries: $d_{mn} = \delta_{mn} 2\xi_b m_b \omega_m$; \mathbf{D}_2 is a $S \times S$ diagonal matrix, with the entries: $d_{pn} = \delta_{pn} 2\xi_p \sqrt{k_p m_p}$; $\mathbf{\Theta}$ is a $S \times S$ diagonal matrix, with the entries: $\Theta_{pn} = \delta_{pn} 2\vartheta_p$; \mathbf{Y} is a $S \times S$ diagonal matrix, with the entries: $Y_{pn} = \delta_{pn} \mathcal{Y}_p$; $\mathbf{F}_B(u_j(t))$ is a $S \times 1$ vector, with the entries: $f_{B_p} = \mathbf{F}_B(u_j(t))$, \mathbf{F}_1 is a $N \times 1$ vector, with the entries $f_m = -w_b(t) \left[\int_{x=0}^{x=L} m_b \phi_m(x) dx + \sum_{j=1}^S m_j \phi(x_j) \right]$, \mathbf{F}_2 is a $S \times 1$ vector, with the entries $f_p = -m_p w_b(t)$ and \mathbf{F}_3 is a $S \times 1$ vector, with the entries $f_p = 0$. For all the indices above, $m, n = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and $p, q = 1, 2, \dots, S$.

The parameters of the resonator mounted at the cantilever beam are derived using an energy method, considering only out-of-plane displacement. The cantilever beam is considered isotropic, while the piezoelectric layers are treated as anisotropic materials, described by the piezoelectric constitutive law: $\sigma = \bar{C}_{11}^E \varepsilon - \bar{e}_{31} E_{\hat{e}_y}$, where ε is the axial strain, \bar{C}_{11}^E is the elastic modulus of the piezoelectric layer at a constant electric field, \bar{e}_{31} is the effective piezoelectric stress constant, and $E_{\hat{e}_y}$ is the electric field component in the \hat{e}_y -direction. The piezoelectric stress constant \bar{e}_{31} is computed using the piezoelectric constant d_{31} as $\bar{e}_{31} = d_{31} \cdot \bar{C}_{11}^E$. The electrical potential function is assumed to vary linearly with the distance between the piezoelectric layers. Using an energy-based approach, the parameters for the j -th resonator are defined as follows (see (54, 55) for details on this

formulation)

$$m_j = m_{beam} \int_0^{l_{beam}} \phi_{beam}(x) dx + (2m_{patch}) \int_0^{l_{patch}} \phi_{beam}(x) dx + M_t, \quad (S37)$$

$$k_j = D_{beam} \int_0^{l_{beam}} \left(\frac{d^2 \phi_{beam}(x)}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx + 2D_{patch} \int_0^{l_{patch}} \left(\frac{d^2 \phi_{beam}(x)}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx, \quad (S38)$$

$$\vartheta_j = B \int_0^{l_{patch}} \frac{d^2 \phi_{beam}(x)}{dx^2} dx, \quad (S39)$$

$$C_{p,j} = 4 \frac{\varepsilon_{33}^S l_{patch} b_{patch}}{2h_{patch}}, \quad (S40)$$

$$B = \bar{e}_{31} b_{patch} \frac{\left((h_{beam}/2 + h_{polyimide} + h_{steel} + h_{pzt})^2 - (h_{beam}/2 + h_{polyimide} + h_{steel})^2 \right)}{2h_{pzt}}, \quad (S41)$$

$$D_{beam} = EI_{beam}, \quad (S42)$$

$$D_{patch} = D_{polyimide} + D_{steel} + D_{pzt} + D_{copper} + D_{polyester}, \quad (S43)$$

where m_{beam} and m_{patch} represent the mass per unit length of the resonator beam and the piezoelectric patch, respectively. M_t is the added tip mass. The term ϕ_{beam} refers to the mass normalized mode shapes of the cantilever beam, as defined by Eq. S29, but calculated using the physical properties of the resonator beam.

The piezoelectric patch used in this prototype, according to the manufacturer, consists of multiple layers arranged as follows (from bottom to top): polyimide, stainless steel 304, PZT-5J, copper, and polyester. The bending rigidity of piezoelectric beam is calculated as a composite beam, considering these materials. The symbols l , b , and h represent the length, width, and thickness of each layer. More details about the piezoelectric patch can be found in the datasheet provided by Mide Company.

Numerical procedure

A numerical procedure is implemented to solve the system of second-order ordinary differential equations. The 4th and 5th-order Runge–Kutta method is applied over the time interval $0 \leq t \leq 10s$ using a Matlab code. Relative tolerance of 10^{-6} and absolute tolerance of 10^{-9} are defined to achieve high numerical accuracy.

Equation S35 is expressed in first-order state-space form as

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{A}_1 \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{A}_2 + \mathbf{A}_3(\mathbf{y}), \quad (S44)$$

where

$$\mathbf{y} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z} \\ \dot{\mathbf{Z}} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{A}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \\ -\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{K} & -\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{C} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{A}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{F} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{A}_3(\mathbf{y}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{F}_B(\mathbf{y}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{S45})$$

To integrate the differential equation, the initial conditions of the system are defined at its stable equilibrium point. The initial displacement and velocity of the host beam are 0 mm and 0 mm/s², respectively. The initial displacement of the resonator beam (u_0) depends on its stability configuration. When the resonator is in a monostable configuration, the initial displacement is 0 mm. When the resonator is in a bistable configuration, there are two stable equilibrium points, and the values depend on the distance between the magnets. For our analysis, we select the equilibrium point with the positive value for the initial displacement. The initial velocity (\dot{u}_0) and voltage (v_0) of the resonator beam are 0 mm/s² and 0 V, respectively.

In sweep frequency analysis, we excite the system using a stepped swept-sine wave over a range of frequencies and a fixed amplitude. The initial conditions are updated for each frequency value as described below. For instance, at the first frequency value, the initial conditions are set as previously mentioned, namely ($u_0, \dot{u}_0 = 0, v_0 = 0$). At the n^{th} frequency value, the initial displacement and velocity are updated to correspond their values with the $n^{th}-1$ frequency value. This procedure continued over the entire frequency range. By updating the initial conditions in this form, we quickly achieve the steady-state regime, which helps to reduce the computational cost.

Table S3 shows the values of the parameters of the system, which are adopted based on the geometry and physical properties of the fabricated metastructure.

The transmissibility frequency response is used to investigate the vibration of the metastructure. This analysis is performed when a stepped swept-sine (up-sweeping frequency from 25 Hz to 90 Hz with a step of 0.1 Hz) excited the base of the host beam. Transmissibility is defined as the ratio of the root mean square (RMS) of the steady-state velocity at the tip of the host beam to that at its base in function of excitation frequency Ω_0

$$\text{Transmissibility}(\Omega_0) = \text{RMS} \frac{\dot{w}_t(L, t_{ss})}{\dot{w}_t(0, t_{ss})}, \quad (\text{S46})$$

where t_{ss} is the time interval of the steady-state regime, which corresponds to the last 20% of the total time series, for each frequency step.

Table S3: Summary for values of the parameters of the metastructure with magneto-elastic piezo-electric resonators.

Length of the host beam, L	985 mm
Length of the resonator beam, l_{beam}	85 mm
Length of the piezoelectric patch, l_{patch}	39 mm
Width of the host beam, b	45 mm
Width of the resonator beam, b_{beam}	24 mm
Width of the piezoelectric patch, b_{patch}	23.3 mm
Thickness of the host beam, h	2 mm
Thickness of the resonator beam, h_{beam}	0.5 mm
Thickness of the piezoelectric patch, h_{patch}	0.41 mm
Young's modulus of carbon fiber, E	62 GPa
Density of the carbon fiber, ρ	1335 kg/m ³
Length of the magnet, l_{mag}	2 mm
Magnet moment of magnet A, μ_A	0.08 Am ²
Magnet moment of magnet B, μ_B	0.08 Am ²
Modal damping of the r-th mode of the host beam, ζ_r	0.005
Damping ratio of the resonator beam, ζ_j	0.03
Number of modes in expansion, N	10
Load resistance, R_L	470 k Ω

Figure S8: Nonlinear magnetic force and potential energy for different magnet distances. (A) Magnetic force in \hat{e}_y direction in function of the displacement of the resonator. (B) Potential energy of the resonator under the magnetic force influence.

To investigate the electrical generation, the sum of the RMS voltage dissipated in each resistor is calculated as

$$\text{Total voltage}(\Omega_0) = \sum_{j=1}^S \text{RMS } v_j(t_{ss}). \quad (\text{S47})$$

The RMS of the total power dissipated in a load resistance R_L can also be calculated by

$$\text{Total power}(\Omega_0) = \frac{\text{Total voltage}^2}{R_L}. \quad (\text{S48})$$

The total voltage and power can be used to analyze the electricity generated. The total power is commonly used when studying energy harvesting with distinct load resistances.

Numerical results

Nonlinear magnetic force (Fig. S8A) and potential energy of the resonator (Fig. S8B) are reported as a function of displacement u for different magnet distances. Figure S8A shows that as the distance between the magnets decreases, the magnetic force increases. Figure S8B shows that at distances of 4 mm and 6 mm, the system exhibits bistable potential, where the beam has two stable equilibrium points. At larger distances, the magnetic force decreases, resulting in a monostable potential. At a distance of 10 mm, the system is effectively free from magnetic influence because the magnitude of the magnetic force is nearly zero.

The equations of motion are numerically integrated as defined in the Numerical Procedure subsection. Then, the transmissibility and the total voltage are calculated as a function of the

excitation frequency. We first obtain numerical results for various magnet distances while keeping the distance identical across all resonators in the metastructure.

Figure S9 presents the numerical transmissibility of the system over the frequency for various magnet distance values (from 2 mm to 10 mm). The peaks in the transmissibility correspond to the wave amplification (around the resonance conditions), while the gray region highlights the local resonance bandgap. When the resonators are in the monostable regime at 10 mm (magnet distances), the bandgap region is established in the frequency range of 41 Hz to 59 Hz. As the distance decreases, the bandgap region shifts to lower frequencies; for instance, at a magnet distance of 5 mm, the bandgap is defined from 25 Hz to 40 Hz. At a distance of approximately 4.3 mm, a transition point is reached, where the resonators change from a monostable to a bistable regime. At this point, the bandgap disappears because the magnetic force cancels the elastic force of the resonator beam, causing the resonators to behave with quasi-zero stiffness and locating the bandgap zone at very low frequencies. When the resonators are in a bistable regime and the distance between the magnets decreases, the bandgap region shifts toward higher frequencies.

Figure S10 presents the total voltage harvested by the system over the frequency for various magnet distance values. The maximum recovered energy occurs at the frequencies corresponding to the peaks observed in the transmissibility, which indicates resonance conditions. During the resonance conditions, the oscillation amplitude is high, resulting in increased energy harvesting. In the bandgap region, the energy harvested is lower compared to that harvesting at the resonance conditions due to the attenuation of wave propagation caused by the local resonance bandgap. As the distance between the magnets changes, the total voltage peaks can shift in frequency. The top view of the total voltage surface plot illustrates this behavior. For example, at the bistable regime, there are voltage peaks at higher frequencies, while at the monostable regime, these peaks occur at lower frequencies. Additionally, the bistable condition exhibits multiple peaks across a broad frequency range, whereas the monostable condition has a narrower energy band with higher amplitudes. Thus, in practical applications where the excitation frequency is not well-defined, the bistable metastructure performs better than the monostable metastructure because it can generate energy across a broad frequency range. At 10 mm, where the resonators are in a quasi-linear regime, these peaks decreased in magnitude. The highest energy harvesting peak is achieved at the distance between the magnets of 6 mm and 7 mm.

Figure S9: Transmissibility evaluated numerically over a frequency range between 25-90 Hz. (A) Velocity transmissibility between the tip of the beam and its base for various excitation frequencies and magnet distances. The gray region indicates the bandgap, where the transmissibility is below zero, with the green lines marking the lower (line 1) and upper (line 2) boundaries. (B) Bandgap boundary for different magnet distances. The vertical gray dashed line indicates the numerical transition from bistable to monostable behavior of the resonators. (C) 2D plots of the velocity transmissibility for different magnet distances.

Figure S10: Total voltage evaluated numerically over a frequency range between 25-90 Hz. (A) Total voltage for various excitation frequencies and magnet distances. (B) Top view of the total voltage surface with the bandgap boundary for different magnet distances. The vertical gray dashed line indicates the numerical transition from bistable to monostable behavior of the resonators. (C) 2D plot of the total voltage for different magnet distances with vertical dashed lines indicating the limits of the bandgap region.

Figure S11: Transmissibility and total voltage evaluated numerically over a frequency range between 25-90 Hz in bistable and monostable regimes under different excitation amplitudes. (A-B) Metastructure with bistable resonators at a distance between the magnets of 3 mm. (C-D) Metastructure with monostable resonators at a distance between the magnets of 7 mm.

Figure S11 presents the transmissibility and total voltage of the metastructure for specific distances between the magnets at 3 mm and 7 mm and under different excitation amplitudes. Figure S11A shows the case of bistable resonators (at 7 mm). When the excitation amplitude is sufficiently high, at 16 g, the bandgap region disappears, resulting in a quasi-flat transmissibility response of nearly zero. This indicates that energy propagates along the beam without increasing in amplitude across the frequency. Figure S11B shows that the generated voltage is higher when the excitation is higher. Figure S11C and D show the transmissibility and the total voltage for the monostable configuration (at 3 mm). The responses remain consistent across all excitation amplitudes.

To investigate the amplitude dependence of the metastructure in the bistable regime, we study the dynamic behavior of the system under a fixed excitation frequency inside the bandgap region. The displacement of the resonators, with a distance between the magnets of 3 mm, is shown in Fig. S12A-C for excitation amplitudes of 2 g, 6 g, and 16 g, respectively. The resonators are numbered from 1 to 7, where resonator 1 is located closest to the fixed end of the host beam, and

resonator 7 is located nearest to the free end, as shown in Fig. 1A of the main manuscript. For applied accelerations of 2 g and 6 g, the resonators exhibit intrawell motion. However, at 16 g, the resonators exhibit irregular interwell motion.

Test 0-1 for chaos is applied to classify if the dynamic behaviors, based on the time series, are chaotic or non-chaotic (as detailed in Section Test 0-1 for chaos). Figures S12D, F, and H show the results of the Test 0-1 for chaos for each resonator under excitation amplitudes of 2 g, 6 g, and 16 g, respectively. At accelerations of 2 g and 6 g, the dynamic behavior of all the resonators is classified as period motion, with test values below 0.2. However, at an acceleration of 16 g, the dynamic behavior of all the resonators is classified as chaotic motion, except for resonator 7, which yields an inconclusive test. The findings from Test 0-1 for chaos and the transmissibility under different excitation amplitude indicate that the presence of chaos disrupts the bandgap region. This observation confirms that at high nonlinearity, the bandgap zone disappears.

Figures S12E, G, and I show the root mean square (RMS) voltage for each resonator under excitation amplitudes of 2 g, 6 g, and 16 g, respectively. At an acceleration of 2 g (Fig. S12E), all resonators produce similar energy output. However, moving from the base to the tip, the resonators produce slightly less voltage. For example, resonator 1 generates 0.7 V ($1.04 \mu\text{W}$), while resonator 7 generates 0.65 V ($0.89 \mu\text{W}$). The observed decrease in voltage is attributed to the attenuation of the wave propagation along the length of the meta beam. As the resonators are positioned further from the excitation point, the harvested energy slightly decreases. This pattern is similar at an acceleration of 6 g (Fig. S12G). Resonator 1 generates 0.8 V ($1.36 \mu\text{W}$), and then the energy slightly decreases to 0.6 V ($0.76 \mu\text{W}$) at resonator 7. At an acceleration of 16 g (Fig. S12I), where the resonators exhibit chaotic motions, the energy harvested significantly increases compared to the energy harvested at the acceleration of 2 g and 6 g. Resonator 1 generates 1.6 V ($5.4 \mu\text{W}$). This energy gradually decreases until resonator 6 and drops to 0.8 V ($1.36 \mu\text{W}$) at resonator 7.

The same procedure is repeated to investigate the amplitude dependence of the metastructure in the monostable regime with distances between the magnets fixed at 7 mm. Figure S13 shows the displacement of the resonators, the results of the Test 0-1 for chaos, and the RMS voltage for an acceleration of 2 g, 6 g, and 9 g. For all excitation levels, the monostable resonators do not exhibit chaotic behavior. The times series of the displacement of the resonators show regular motion and the Test 0-1 for chaos confirm their periodic behaviors. The RMS voltage of monostable resonators

Figure S12: Numerical dynamic analysis of the resonators in bistable conditions (distance between the magnets of 3 mm) under different excitation amplitudes and at a fixed frequency of 71 Hz. Time series of the displacement of resonators under (A) 2 g, (B) 6 g, and (C) 16 g. Results of the Test 0-1 for chaos of the resonators under (D) 2 g, (F) 6 g, and (H) 16 g. Root Mean Square (RMS) voltage of the resonators under (E) 2 g, (G) 6 g, and (I) 16 g.

demonstrates that resonator 1, closest to the fixed end of the beam, generates more energy compared to those positioned closer to the tip of the beam across all acceleration levels. For example, at an acceleration of 9 g, resonator 1 generates 6.1 V (79.1 μW), while resonator 7 generates 0.05 V (0.005 μW).

To verify improvement in the system performance, numerical analysis of the proposed metastructure is conducted imposing nonidentical distances between the magnets of the resonators. Seven different configurations, as shown in Fig. S14A-B, are tested.

The normalized performance index, as described in the main manuscript, is calculated for each configuration and shown in Fig. S14C. This index is computed using the numerical performance of the metastructure with all the resonators set at an identical magnet distance of 3 mm as a reference, which provides the widest band performance for the metabeam when all resonators have the same distance. An index value below 1 indicates that the metastructure with identical resonators at a distance of 3 mm performs better, while a value above 1 indicates that the metastructure with non-identical resonators has superior performance. Moreover, we calculate this index for the combined metrics (taking into account the performance of the vibration attenuation and the energy harvesting) and the individual performance of vibration attenuation and energy harvesting. The results show that configurations 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 7 have superior combined metrics, while configuration 6 performs worse. The results show that configurations 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 have superior attenuation performance, while configuration 6 and 7 perform worse. The results show that configurations 1, 3, 4, 6 and 7 have superior harvesting performance, while configuration 2 and 5 perform slightly worse.

Figures S14D illustrates the bandgap regions for the seven configurations. Figures S14E shows the transmissibility response for configurations 2 and 4. These results demonstrate that in addition to broadening the bandgap, the metastructures with resonators having nonidentical magnet distances are capable of attenuating multiple modal frequencies with several separated bandgap regions.

Figure S14F shows the total energy harvested for configurations 2 and 4. The results indicate that the energy harvesting performance can be improved when the resonators having nonidentical magnet distances by broadening the frequency band and shifting the voltage peaks in frequency.

Figure S13: Numerical dynamic analysis of the resonators in monostable conditions (distance between the magnets of 7 mm) under different excitation amplitudes and at a fixed frequency of 45 Hz. Time series of the displacement of resonators under (A) 2 g, (B) 6 g, and (C) 9 g. Results of the Test 0-1 for chaos of the resonators under (D) 2 g, (F) 6 g, and (H) 9 g. Root Mean Square (RMS) voltage of the resonators under (E) 2 g, (G) 6 g, and (I) 9 g.

Figure S14: Vibration suppression and energy harvesting performance evaluated numerically with resonators having nonidentical magnet distances. (A) Schematic representation. (B) Configurations diagram. (C) Numerical normalized performance index (NPI) of the metastructure for the tested configurations, considering the bandwidth of the bandgap and the total energy harvested across the frequency spectrum. A combined performance index, integrating both metrics, is also shown. (D) Numerical bandgap regions for the tested configurations, where the dots mark frequency ranges with transmissibility below zero. (E) Numerical transmissibility as a function of frequency for configurations 2 and 4. (F) Numerical total voltage as a function of frequency for configurations 2 and 4.

Fabrication and assembly of the physical prototype

The host beam is fabricated by cutting a carbon fiber plate (with dimensions of $985 \times 45 \times 2$ mm³) using a CNC engraving machine (Roland EGX 600). Seven uniformly spaced holes, each measuring 118×30 mm² precisely aligned along the central axis of the beam, are perforated using the same CNC machine.

For the cloaking proposal, reinforcement grids are also fabricated from carbon fiber using the CNC machine. Its dimensions are defined as specified in Section of Cloaking Design ($b_x = 7.1$ mm, $\bar{b}_x = 1$ mm, $b_y = 2.1$ mm, and $h_t = 1.1$ mm). A total of seven pairs of reinforcements are prepared. They are bonded to encircle the voids on both sides of the beam to preserve the symmetry. Before bonding them on the host beam, a surface treatment of the bonding faces is carried out, which involves contaminant removal using detergents and isopropyl alcohol, followed by abrasion with sandpaper. A structural adhesive (3M Scotch-Weld DP460) is applied to bond the reinforcements, and the assembly is left to cure for 24 hours at 25°C.

The resonator beams are also made up carbon fiber, with dimensions of $95 \times 24 \times 0.5$ mm³, using the CNC machine. Two piezoelectric layers (S118-J1SS-1808YB, Mide Technology) are bonded on both sides of each resonator beam using the same structural adhesive and bonding procedure. The piezoelectric layers are positioned near the fixed end of the resonator beams, a region of high deformation, to maximize energy conversion.

The piezoelectric resonator beams are mounted on the host beam and precisely positioned inside the hole, aligned along the neutral axis. The reinforcement bar is used to clamp the resonator in place. Two M2 bolts are carefully tightened to secure longitudinal and transverse movement constraints at the clamped region without overtightening, preventing potential damage to the piezo. The deflection resonator part is positioned inside the larger section of the hole, while the smaller section allows easy access to electrical mounting. The effective length of each piezoelectric beam remains 85 mm.

A permanent cylindrical magnet (Neodymium Magnet NdFeB with a diameter of 8 mm and a height of 2 mm, magnetized in the axial direction) is attached to the tip of the beam using a 3D-printed holder, manufactured with a Stratasys Origin One Printer. An identical magnet is mounted on the host beam in front of the first magnet using an adjustable 3D-printed holder. The magnets

are positioned with the same poles facing each other to generate a repulsive magnetic force, as previously described. The adjustable holder enables precise control of the distance between the magnets. A bolt is used to securely fix the holder at the desired distance during testing.

A custom 3D-printed connector is designed to support the electrode connections of the piezo patches. It is fixed using the same M2 bolts as the resonator clamp and aligned with the positive and negative conductive regions of the piezo, ensuring proper electrical contact with the wires. A 22-gauge cable is fixed with a small bolt to keep the connections. The cables are organized on a protoboard, with the piezo patches of each resonator connected in parallel. This parallel connection doubles the current output while maintaining the same voltage. A load resistor of 470 k Ω is also connected in parallel to the piezo terminals, to properly measure the harvested energy. Each resonator has its dedicated electrical circuit, and there are no electrical connections between the seven circuits.

Figure S15 shows a detailed drawing of the proposed metastructure, including all assembling components. Movie S6 shows an exploded animation of the system assembly. Figure 5 of the main manuscript shows photos of the fabricated metastructure.

Vibration experiments

Experimental setup

Vibration tests are conducted using a shaker TIRA Vib 51144 (frequency range: 2-6500 Hz, rated peak force SINE/RANDOM: 440 N, maximum rated travel: 25.4 mm), equipped with a Power Amplifier TIRA BAA 1000 (frequency range: 2-20000 Hz) and mounted on a Nexus Optical Table from Thorlabs. The amplifier is connected to a vibration controller hardware VR9500 (4 channels, 26000 lines of resolution) to apply a controlled sine excitation. An accelerometer PCB 356A45 (ICP, sensitivity: 99.8 mV/g, measurement range: ± 50 g peak, frequency range: 0.4 to 10 kHz) is used to measure the base acceleration of the metastructure. This sensor provides a feedback signal for a closed-loop control. A sine module software VibrationVIEW is used to interface the controlled excitation. A sine sweep (from 23 Hz to 90 Hz, linear sweep rate of 3 Oct/min, and a fixed acceleration amplitude) is generated to investigate the metastructure behavior over a frequency range.

A 3D Digital Image Correlation (DIC-3D) system is used to measure the full-field displacement

Figure S15: Illustration of the cloaked metastructure with the magneto-elastic piezoelectric resonators. (A) Drawing of the metastructure. (B) Zoomed-in view of the cloaking design and the magneto-elastic piezoelectric resonator. (C) Exploded-view drawing of all assembly parts.

of the metastructure. This system consists of two high-speed Photron Fastcam Nova S9 (1024x1024 pixel @ 9000 fps) arranged in a stereo configuration to achieve three-dimensional measurement. The cameras are positioned on adjustable tripods at an angle of approximately 30° relative to the specimen and with a distance of 55 cm between them. They are also placed 90 cm far from the center of the specimen. The intrinsic and extrinsic parameters, which include the focal length, lens distortion, stereo angle, image scale, and image center, are defined to maximize the measurement performance. A calibration process is conducted using a calibration target (grid pattern) to define the stereoscopic relationship between the two cameras. The final calibrated setup ensures measurement accuracy with a projection error below 0.1 pixels and a precise spatial measurement.

A speckle pattern pattern is generated using a speckle generator software that randomly creates distributed black dots on a white background. The size of the speckles is chosen to ensure that each dot covers a diameter of 3 to 5 pixels in the captured images. Using a resolution camera of 1 MP and a field of view of 1 m^2 , our ratio between space and camera resolution is 1 mm/pixel. Thus, the dot diameter must be between 3 mm and 5 mm. We select a diameter of 4 mm. They are randomly distributed with a standard deviation of 75%. The speckle pattern is printed on adhesive sticker paper and carefully bound to the surface of the metastructure to provide accurate 3D displacement tracking.

During the experiments, images are captured at a sampling rate of 1000 fps. The trigger of the cameras is synchronized with the shaker excitation. The exposure time is adjusted to avoid motion blur (1/1000 s). Two blue lights are used to enhance the visibility of the speckle pattern on the surface by increasing the contrast between the speckled surface and the background. These lights are strategically positioned to minimize shadows, enhance image contrast, and avoid glare.

The DIC processing is performed using VIC-3D software. This analysis involves tracking the full-field displacement in three dimensions. The software computes the displacement field by comparing the reference (undeformed) image with subsequent deformed images during the test. The subset size of 21x21 and step size of 4 pixels are carefully chosen for accurate displacement calculations, ensuring a good balance between resolution and noise sensitivity.

To measure the voltage dissipated across each resistor, we connect voltage probes with a 10x attenuation at each load resistor. The attenuation is applied to prevent overloading in the measurement system by reducing the voltage signal before acquisition. The BNC connectors of the

Figure S16: Illustration of the experimental apparatus and signal flow diagram for testing the proposed metastructure.

probes are linked to a data acquisition system (DAQ, input range of $\pm 10V$, 7-input channels, from Correlated Solutions). The DAQ is configured to operate in synchronous mode with the DIC system, obtaining synchronized measurements between the analog voltage data and the captured image. The voltage data and displacement fields are recorded at the same sampling rate: 1000 Hz for sweep frequency experiments and 2000 Hz for fixed frequency experiments. This synchronization ensures that the voltage measurements and the corresponding mechanical displacement are accurately recorded at the same time.

Figure S16 shows an illustration of the experimental apparatus and signal flow diagram used during the experimental analysis of the metastructure to measure the full-field displacement and the voltage of each resonator under a controlled base motion excitation.

Figure S17 presents images of the experimental apparatus, including details of the metastructure coated with the speckle pattern and the experimental setup.

Experimental results

Figure S17: (A) Photo of the metastructure covered by the speckle pattern. The red-marked region shows a zoomed-in view of the black dots with a diameter of 4 mm. (B-C) Photo of the experimental setup without and with blue lights, respectively. These photos demonstrate the positions of the cameras, blue lights, and the the metastructure mounted on the shaker.

The experimental tests are performed to validate the numerical results. A 3D-printed graduated scale is employed to accurately set the distance between the magnets. The tests are conducted following the procedure outlined in the previous section. For the bistable configuration of the resonators, an acceleration amplitude of 2 g is applied, whereas for the monostable configuration, an acceleration amplitude of 6 g is applied. A lower acceleration is chosen for the bistable condition to prevent chaotic motion in the resonators.

The transmissibility response is derived during post-processing. The power spectral density (PSD) is estimated from the velocity response measured under chirp-up excitation. A Hanning window is used to divide the signal into four segments, with a 50% overlap between the segments. The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is computed using the same sampling frequency as the acquisition system. The transmissibility is then obtained by taking the ratio of the PSD of velocity at the tip of the beam to that at the base.

The voltage generated across the frequency range is calculated using the same PSD estimation process. However, before applying the FFT, the signal is multiplied by a factor of 10 to compensate

for the 10x attenuation introduced by the probes. To mitigate the amplification of electrical noise caused by this multiplication, a filter with a low pass band is also applied to the signal.

Initially, all resonators are configured with identical distances between the magnets. Various values of the magnet distances are tested. Experimental transmissibility of the metastructure for various magnet distances are shown in Fig. S18. The figure illustrates the transmissibility surface across a range of frequencies. The velocity transmissibility peaks correspond to the amplitude amplification of the tip of the beam. The gray region defines the local resonance bandgap. Similar to the numerical results, the experimental tests confirmed that as the magnet distance decreases, the bandgap shifts toward higher frequencies.

The quasi-zero stiffness condition close to the transition point, from monostable to bistable regimes, is not observed in experiments. This is due to 1 mm increments in magnet distance during testing, along with geometric asymmetries and manufacturing uncertainties of the system, that prevent the precise replication of this condition in the experimental results. However, the results show that as the magnet distance approaches the transition point coming from the monostable regime, the bandgap shifts to lower frequencies. This suggests that the magnetic force weakened the elastic force, moving the bandgap to lower frequencies, consistent with numerical results near quasi-zero stiffness.

Figure S19 shows the power spectrum density (PSD) of the total voltage generated by the system. The experimental results aligned with the previously presented numerical results. As the magnet distance changes, the total voltage peaks shift in frequency. The bistable condition shows multiple peaks across a broad frequency range, while the monostable condition shows a narrower energy band with more prominent peaks. The optimal energy harvesting peaks are observed for the metastructure with magnet distances of 5 mm and 7 mm.

Nonlinear system exhibits multiple responses, which can change drastically depending on the conditions. For example, bistable oscillators typically present intrawell and interwell motions, varying from regular to irregular behaviors, only changing the initial conditions or amplitude of excitation. Therefore, understanding the behavior of this structure across different responses is crucial.

The most sensitive parameters for exploring multiple solutions are the initial conditions and the amplitude of excitation. Given the significant challenge of controlling the initial conditions

Figure S18: Experimental transmissibility frequency response under varying magnet distances. (A) Transmissibility of the velocity at the tip of the beam relative to its base across a range of frequencies, shown for different magnet distances. The gray region highlights the bandgap, where the transmissibility is below zero. Green lines mark the lower boundary (line 1) and the upper boundary (line 2) of the bandgap. (B) Bandgap boundary lines as a function of magnet distance. The vertical gray dashed line represents the transition from bistable to monostable behavior of the resonators. (C) A 2D plot of the transmissibility for different magnet distances.

Figure S19: Experimental voltage output for varying magnet distances. (A) Power Spectrum Density (PSD) surface of the total voltage harvested, normalized by the acceleration amplitude, across a range of frequencies for different magnet distances. (B) Top view of the PSD surface, showing the bandgap boundary lines for each magnet distance. (C) 2D plot of the PSD of the total voltage for different magnet distances. Vertical dashed lines indicate the boundaries of the bandgap region.

experimentally, this study focuses on varying the amplitude of excitation. The amplitude of excitation can significantly influence the behavior of the system. For instance, when a bistable oscillator is subjected to low excitation amplitudes, the external energy is insufficient to overcome the potential barrier, resulting in oscillation around a single stable equilibrium point. As the external energy increases, the oscillation starts alternating between stable points in either regular or irregular ways. Thus, to investigate how excitation amplitude affects the performance of this metastructure, we test the system under different acceleration amplitudes, specifically 2 g, 6 g, and 9 g, with the resonators configured at a magnet distance of 3 mm (bistable) and 7 mm (monostable).

Figures S20A-B show the transmissibility for the metastructure when the resonators are under bistable and monostable conditions, respectively. In the bistable condition, we observe that at high excitation amplitudes of 9 g, the bandgap region disappears. The transmissibility response at this condition is nearly flat, with a magnitude close to 1. This indicates that the elastic wave propagation along the beam is not significantly amplified, showing only minor amplification but not comparable to the amplification observed under resonance conditions. At lower excitation amplitudes of 2 g and 6 g, the bandgap is still present. Notably, at 6 g, there are some narrow frequency bands where the transmissibility exceeds one. On the other hand, in the monostable case, the bandgap region remains consistent and clearly defined, regardless of the excitation amplitude.

Figures S20C-D show the PSD of the total voltage, normalized by the acceleration amplitude, for the metastructure when the resonators are under bistable and monostable conditions, respectively. In the bistable configuration, the voltage generation at 9 g has higher voltages in a wide spectrum, allowing the system to generate electricity over a broader frequency range. However, as shown in Figures S20A, at 9 g, the bandgap region disappeared. For applications that do not require bandgap formation and primarily focus on energy harvesting, this condition demonstrates the widest energy harvesting range. In the monostable configuration, the voltage peaks are similar for all acceleration tested, with energy concentrated at higher peaks within a narrower frequency range.

A single fixed-frequency excitation test is conducted to investigate the dynamic behavior at the local resonance bandgap condition for different acceleration values. Frequencies of 71 Hz and 45 Hz are used to excite the bistable and monostable configurations, respectively, that correspond to the frequency value within their respective bandgap zones. The sampling frequency for the measurement is increased to 2000 Hz to improve the signal resolution. A high time resolution is

Figure S20: Amplitude-dependence of the metastructure in bistable and monostable regimes. Experimental transmissibility frequency response at acceleration levels of 2 g, 6 g, and 9 g for (A) the bistable regime (magnet distance of 3 mm) and (B) the monostable regime (magnet distance of 7 mm). Dashed vertical lines at 71 Hz for the bistable case and 45 Hz for the monostable case indicate the bandgap frequencies studied further below. The PSD of the total harvested voltage, normalized by acceleration amplitude, is shown under 2 g, 6 g, and 9 g excitations for the (C) bistable and (D) monostable configurations.

essential for the time series analysis. The displacement and velocity responses of the resonators, along with the generated voltage, are measured.

We use the Poincaré map of these time series to experimentally verify and characterize the dynamic behavior of the resonators. The Poincaré map is a common method in dynamical systems analysis to investigate the projection of the trajectory of the system onto a low-dimensional subspace. Thus, we calculate the map by selecting a cross-section of its phase space that corresponds to the excitation frequency and observing the evolution of state points on that cross-section (56). The resulting map helps distinguish between periodic and irregular system responses. For example, when the trajectory intersects the cross-section at a single point, the system exhibits regular behavior with a period-1. Two intersection points indicate a period-2, while multiple intersections suggest an irregular motion. This analysis provides a deeper understanding of the dynamic characteristics of the system.

To calculate the intersection points for the Poincaré map, we increase the time resolution of the response by using spline interpolation. This approach is effective due to the already high sampling frequency of the time series. However, it is necessary to ensure that there are enough samples available to accurately characterize the dynamic behavior. To further enhance the quality of the signal, we apply a Savitzky-Golay filter with a polynomial order of 3 and a frame length of 13 points. This filter helps to remove noise disturbances from the measurements. Additionally, we use singular value decomposition to reconstruct a denoised time series by truncating smaller singular values. This combined methodology significantly improves the overall signal quality, minimizing noise interference that could impact the construction of the Poincaré map while preserving the dynamic characteristics of the motion.

Figure S21 shows the phase space of displacement and velocity with the Poincaré maps for resonators in the bistable configuration (magnet distance of 3 mm) under accelerations of 2 g, 6 g, and 9 g, with a fixed frequency excitation of 71 H. For 2 g and 6 g, the resonators exhibit a single orbit with one intersection point, indicating a periodic motion with one period. Notably, the first resonator has a higher energy orbit compared to those located closer to the tip of the beam. This occurs because the energy propagation within the bandgap is attenuated along the length of the structure, resulting in weaker excitation for the resonators nearer to the tip. Additionally, we observe stable orbits concentric to the equilibrium point (near 0 mm displacement), characterizing periodic

intrawell motion for all resonators. At excitation of 9 g, the results show irregular motions, as indicated by multiple intersection points on the Poincaré map. The resonators have multiple orbits with varying energy levels, concentric to two equilibrium points at 0 mm and 5 mm. This behavior indicates irregular interwell motion. This high amplitude of oscillation is observed for all resonators, indicating that energy is not attenuating along the length of the beam. It confirms that for high excitations, the bandgap disappears. The phase spaces also reveal asymmetry in the restoring force between one stable equilibrium point and another because the orbits around one equilibrium point show more energy than those around the other. This asymmetry is especially evident in resonators 1, 3, and 5 and can be attributed to geometric variations, assembly imperfections, material properties, or manufacturing uncertainties.

Figure S22 shows the phase space of displacement and velocity with the Poincaré maps for resonators in the monostable configuration (magnet distance of 7 mm) under accelerations of 2 g, 6 g, and 9 g, with a fixed frequency excitation of 45 Hz. In all accelerations, the resonators exhibit a single orbit with one intersection point, indicating a periodic motion with one period. The first resonator has a higher energy orbit compared to those located closer to the tip of the beam. There is no indication of irregular motion. The orbits for all resonators are concentric around a single equilibrium point, confirming the monostable regime.

To confirm the presence of chaotic behavior, we apply the Test 0-1 for chaos. Details of this test can be seen in Section Test 0-1 for chaos. We use a sampling of 1000 to guarantee convergence of the classifier.

Figure S23 shows the results of this test for the displacement of the resonators under 2 g, 6 g, and 9 g. Figure S23A shows the results for the bistable resonators. At 2 g and 6 g, the values of the test are below 0.2, classifying the motion of the resonators as periodic. At 9 g, the values of the test are above 0.8, indicating chaotic motion. Figure S23B shows the results for the monostable resonators. For all excitation levels, the values of the test are below 0.2, classifying the dynamic series as periodic. Therefore, according to Test 0-1 for chaos based on the time series of the resonators and the observations from the transmissibility, we confirm that the presence of chaos on the response of the resonators disrupts the local resonance bandgap.

The experimental findings are consistent with the numerical results. Both analyses indicate that this chaotic behavior disrupts bandgap formation, resulting in a structure that has a passband

Figure S21: Phase portrait and Poincaré map for bistable resonators under accelerations of 2 g, 6 g, and 9 g at a frequency of 71 Hz. The phase portrait orbits are represented by gray lines, while the Poincaré points are shown as orange dots. The first column displays the results for an acceleration of 2 g, the second column for 6 g, and the third column for 9 g. The resonators are presented from top to bottom, with resonator 1 at the top and resonator 7 at the bottom.

Figure S22: Phase portrait and Poincaré map for monostable resonators under accelerations of 2 g, 6 g, and 9 g at a frequency of 45 Hz. The phase portrait orbits are represented by gray lines, while the Poincaré points are shown as orange dots. The first column displays the results for an acceleration of 2 g, the second column for 6 g, and the third column for 9 g. The resonators are presented from top to bottom, with resonator 1 at the top and resonator 7 at the bottom.

Figure S23: Test 0-1 for chaos based on the experimental displacement of the resonators at (A) bistable and (B) monostable configurations under **under** accelerations of 2 g, 6 g, and 9 g.

but without wave amplification. Additionally, in terms of energy harvesting, experimental and numerical results confirm that under the chaotic behavior of the resonators, the energy generation improves when compared to the bandgap condition. It is indicated by the oscillations of higher amplitudes under chaotic motion.

In the following, the metastructure with resonators with nonidentical distance between the magnet is tested. Seven configurations using combined bistable and monostable resonators are tested, as shown in Fig. S24A. These configurations are particularly defined to incorporate the benefits of using bistable systems with monostable systems.

The transmissibility and PSD of the total generated voltage responses for each configuration are plotted in Fig. S24. These configurations effectively create a wide bandgap, or even multiple bandgap zones, demonstrating their capability to attenuate multiple frequencies and vibrational modes. For example, configuration 2 exhibits a bandgap starting around 40 Hz and extending to approximately 73, and configuration 5 exhibits bandgap zones starting at 40 Hz and ending at 82 Hz. Narrow peaks with low amplitudes are observed between the transitions from the first to the second bandgap regions for these configurations.

Based on our previous analysis, bistable resonators are responsible for generating bandgaps at higher frequencies, while monostable resonators are responsible for lower frequencies. Compared to the metastructure using the resonators with identical magnet distances, the use of nonidentical magnetic distances improves the vibration suppression performance.

In terms of energy harvesting, the nonidentical cases produce more voltage peaks, indicating an increased capability to harvest energy across a wider range of frequency bands. For instance,

in Configuration 4, in addition to presenting multiple voltage peaks, these peaks exhibit a broad frequency range. This performance is essential for enhancing harvesting performance in practical applications.

In the sequence, we compare the performance of these configurations to a metastructure with resonators at identical magnet distances. The magnetic distance of 3 mm is chosen for comparison because it showed the widest band for the bandgap and energy harvesting.

We calculate an index, called the Normalized Performance Index (NPI), which considers the bandgap bandwidth and the total voltage output across the entire tested frequency spectrum. The NPI is defined as

$$\text{NPI}_i = \varepsilon \frac{\text{BG}_i}{\text{BG}_3} + \chi \frac{\text{EH}_i}{\text{EH}_3} \quad (\text{S49})$$

where BG_i and EH_i are the bandgap bandwidth and the total harvested voltage for the configuration i , respectively. BG_3 and EH_3 are the same parameters for the metastructure with identical resonators at a magnet distance of 3 mm. The parameters ε and χ are the weights to define the importance of vibration attenuation and energy generation, respectively. These weights are defined between 0 and 1, such as $\varepsilon + \chi = 1$. When ε and χ are both set to 0.5, it is a combined metric that considers the vibration attenuation and energy generation equally important.

When the NPI is below one, the metastructure with identical magnet distances at 3 mm performs better. When the NPI is above one, the metastructure with nonidentical magnet distances is superior.

Figure S25 presents the NPI for all configurations tested. Configuration 4 performs the best energy harvesting performance. However, its performance for vibration mitigation is lower compared to that for identical resonators. Configuration 5 performs the highest performance in vibration attenuation but shows the lowest energy harvesting efficiency among the configurations. A noticeable trade-off pattern occurs across all configurations; as vibration suppression improves, the voltage decreases. This relationship is expected because if the oscillation of the beam decreases, the energy converted is lower. The combined metric shows a balanced performance that takes into account the vibration suppression and energy harvesting abilities. Configuration 2 provides the highest combined metric, achieving a broad bandgap without significantly compromising electrical conversion efficiency.

Additionally, these results illustrate the ability of the metastructure to change the magnet

Figure S24: Vibration absorption and energy harvesting performance of the metastructure using nonidentical resonators. (A) Configurations tested varying the magnet distance of the resonators. Transmissibility response (top) and the PSD of the total voltage harvested (bottom) for the configurations: (B) 1, (C) 2, (D) 3, (E) 4, (F) 5, (G) 6 and (H) 7. The vertical dashed line delimited the bandgap regions in the voltage spectrum graphs.

Figure S25: Normalized Performance Index (NPI) of the metastructure for each configuration, considering individual performance for the bandwidth of the bandgap and the total energy harvested across the spectrum and their combination performance with the same importance scale.

distance and prioritize vibration attenuation or energy harvesting. For example, for prioritized vibration attenuation, configuration 5 is most suitable, while configuration 4 is ideal for energy generation.

Finally, the numerical and experimental results demonstrate that using nonidentical magnet distances paves the way to improve the performance of the metastructure compared to the system using identical distances.

Lighting activation via energy harvesting

To demonstrate the energy harvesting capabilities of our metastructure, we power seven LEDs using the voltage generated from vibrations of the system. We connect yellow LEDs (with a forward voltage drop of 2 V and a forward current of 20 mA) in parallel with a resistor corresponding to each resonator, so each resonator powers a single LED. This setup also allows us to visually observe the energy generation intensity of each resonator.

This test is conducted for the metastructure with an identical magnet distance of 7 mm. We increase the excitation amplitude from 0 g to 9 g, with a constant frequency of 31 Hz, the resonance condition for this configuration. Figure S26 shows sequences of pictures of the powered LEDs at different instants of time and acceleration. The LEDs are arranged in line with the resonators from left to right, such as resonator 1 is nearest the beam base and resonator 7 closest to the tip. At lower excitation levels, the LEDs powered by the first resonators are the first to turn on. As the excitation amplitude increases, the remaining LEDs are turned on. Notably, some LEDs appear brighter than others, which we attribute to their positions along the beam. For example, LEDs powered by resonators closer to node points of the vibrational mode at a certain excitation frequency receive less excitation energy, generating less power.

In this test, we generate a voltage of 5.3 V and a power output of 46.6 μW when the acceleration is 8 g. This energy can be rectified using electronic circuits to convert alternating current into direct current, making it suitable for powering various microelectronic devices. Examples include microcontrollers, wireless sensors in sleep mode for temperature and humidity monitoring, low-power OLED displays, and more. Additionally, this energy can be utilized to recharge batteries, thereby expanding its applicability across a wider range of devices. With advancements in electronic engineering, particularly in minimizing voltage drops during the rectification process, the potential of this technology can increase significantly. As these technologies advance, energy harvesting from vibrations will become more efficient and effective, enabling wider utilization across diverse applications.

Figure S26: Frame sequence from a test demonstrating LEDs powered by energy harvested (EH) from the resonators during vibration excitation. Frame 1 is captured at 0 s with an acceleration of 0 g, while subsequent frames show accelerations increasing to 3 g at 8 s, 6 g at 9 s, and 8 g at 13 s.

Test 0-1 for chaos

Test 0-1 for chaos is a statistical method based on time-series analysis to classify the dynamic behavior of the resonators. Unlike the Lyapunov exponent method, which requires phase space reconstruction and eigenvalue calculation at a high computational cost, the 0-1 Test for chaos offers a more computationally efficient approach (57). This method identifies chaotic or non-chaotic behavior by performing an Euclidean extension transformation of the time series. A statistical classifier, derived from the covariance and variance of these transformed coordinates, is then used to categorize the dynamic behavior (48). Classifier values below 0.2 indicate regular motion, while values above 0.8 suggest chaotic behavior. Values between 0.2 and 0.8 are considered inconclusive. This methodology is applied to the displacement time series of the resonators.

The 0-1 test for chaos maps the time series $x(t)$ into a pair of transformed coordinates:

$$p_n(c) = \sum_{j=1}^n x(t_j) \cos(jc), \quad (\text{S50})$$

$$q_n(c) = \sum_{j=1}^n x(t_j) \sin(jc), \quad (\text{S51})$$

where c is a random value uniformly drawn from the interval $[0, 2\pi)$ and $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$. For regular (non-chaotic) behavior, the coordinates display bounded motion, while in chaotic systems, they asymptotically resemble Brownian motion.

The mean square deviation

$$M_n(c) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \left([p_{j+n}(c) - p_j(c)]^2 + [q_{j+n}(c) - q_j(c)]^2 \right) \quad (\text{S52})$$

is used to identify diffusive or non-diffusive behavior. The classifier

$$K_c = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\text{Cov}(\bar{t}_n, \bar{M}_n)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(\bar{t}_n) \text{Var}(\bar{M}_n)}}, \quad (\text{S53})$$

where $\bar{M}_n = (M_1, M_2, \dots, M_n)$, $\bar{t}_n = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n)$, Cov and Var denoting covariance and variance operators, is computed for several values of c . The median result is taken to classify the dynamic behavior as chaotic ($K > 0.8$), regular ($K < 0.2$), or inconclusive ($0.2 < K < 0.8$).

Caption for Movie S1. Metastructure test for powering seven LEDs using the vibration source. The video shows a vibration test of the metastructure with monostable resonators at a magnet distance of 7 mm excited at a fixed frequency of 29 Hz. The test sweeps up and down the amplitude of excitation from 0 g to 8 g. The LEDs are arranged in line with the resonators from left to right, with resonator 1 nearest the beam base and resonator 7 closest to the tip.

Caption for Movie S2. Vibration test of the metastructure with monostable resonators at a magnet distance of 7 mm. The video shows the metastructure response to a fixed excitation frequency under resonance condition at 31 Hz and bandgap condition at 45 Hz.

Caption for Movie S3. Vibration test of the metastructure with bistable resonators at a magnet distance of 3 mm. The video shows the metastructure response to a fixed excitation frequency under resonance condition at 31 Hz and bandgap condition at 71 Hz.

Caption for Movie S4. Vibration test of the metastructure with bistable resonators at a magnet distance of 3 mm under increasing the excitation amplitude within the bandgap region. The video demonstrates the amplitude dependence of the metastructure with bistable resonators. The test is conducted at a fixed frequency of 71 Hz while gradually increasing the amplitude from 2 g to 10 g. At lower amplitudes, the bandgap phenomenon is observed; however, as the amplitude increases, the bandgap effect disappears, and the resonators show chaotic motion.

Caption for Movie S5. Digital image correlation results from the vibration test. The video shows the metastructure responses using the 3D digital image correlation.

Caption for Movie S6. Assembly of the metastructure: exploded view animation. The video provides a detailed demonstration of the metastructure assembly.